

TABLE I—FORMATION CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF Be(II) COMPLEXES

Complex	Temp. °C	log K ₁	log K ₂	-ΔF ₁ (k cal/mole)	-ΔF ₂ (k cal/mole)	-ΔH (k cal/mole)	ΔS e.u.
5-Chloro salicylate	30	11.05	7.35	15.42	10.26	48.05	-107.7
	35	10.60	7.20	15.04	10.21		
	40	9.95	7.10	14.34	10.24		
5-Amino salicylate	30	14.40	6.90	20.10	9.63	21.84	-5.7
	35	14.10	6.00	20.00	8.51		
	40	13.90	6.50	20.04	9.37		
5-Sulpho salicylate	30	9.70	5.90	13.54	8.23	21.84	-27.4
	35	9.40	5.40	10.50	7.66		
	40	9.20	5.20	13.26	7.50		

binding in these complexes⁶. If the structure of

the complexes were $-\text{C}=\text{O}-\text{M}$, we should observe the characteristic $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ frequency at about 1720 cm^{-1} in place of carboxylate frequency observed at about 1600 cm^{-1} . The absence of a band near 1720 cm^{-1} indicates that the carboxylate to metal bond is essentially ionic.

The presence of lattice water can only be confirmed by the appearance of band below 500 cm^{-1} ⁷. Because of the instrumental range used we could not confirm the presence of lattice water. However, the absence of a band at 800 cm^{-1} , which is observed in all the complexes in which water is coordinated, indicates the presence of lattice water and that water present is not coordinated⁸.

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Polarographic Study of Tl(I)- α,α' -Bipyridyl System

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BIPYRIDYL complexes of Tl(I) in aqueous media have been reported using different analytical techniques^{1,2}. The effect of organic solvents on the polarographic behaviour of Tl(I) has been studied by Singh *et al.*³. A survey of literature

reveals that the Tl(I)-bipyridyl system has not been studied polarographically in different aquo-organic media. The present communication presents the result of polarographic study of bipyridyl complexes of Tl(I) in aquo and 50% aquo-organic (dimethylformamide, ethyl acetate, ethanol and dioxane) media.

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals were used. Solutions of Tl(I) and α,α' -bipyridyl were prepared in double distilled water. The test solutions containing $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ Tl(I) and different concentrations of α,α' -bipyridyl were prepared in such a way that the DMF, dioxane, ethanol and ethyl acetate to water ratio in each case was 50% (v/v). Sodium perchlorate was used as supporting electrolyte ($\mu=1.0$) and gelatin (0.001%) as maximum suppressor.

Polarograms were recorded on a C.I.C. (Baroda), automatic pen recording polarograph. Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the test solution to remove the dissolved oxygen. The capillary had the following characteristics, $m=2.65$ mg/sec, $t=3.0$ sec, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.3$ $\text{mg}^{2/3} \text{sec}^{-1/6}$ (in 1.0 M NaClO₄, open circuit), $h_{\text{corr}} = 35.0$ cm. An Elico digital pH meter (model, L1-120) was used to measure the pH. All the observations were made at room temperature $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Hydrochloric acid/sodium hydroxide solutions were used to adjust the pH of the test solutions at 8.00, and the test solutions were deaerated with pure nitrogen gas.

Results and Discussion

In the presence of increasing concentrations (0.5×10^{-3} to $1 \times 10^{-3} M$) of α,α' -bipyridyl Tl(I) gave a well-defined one electron reduction wave at $\mu=1.0$ (NaClO₄) and pH 8.00 in aqueous and 50% aquo-organic media. The reduction of Tl(I) in presence of increasing concentration of α,α' -bipyridyl was found to be reversible in aqueous and aquo-organic media except for the ethyl acetate medium. The reduction of Tl(I) in ethyl acetate medium was reversible at low concentrations of the ligand while it tended to be of quasireversible nature with increasing ligand concentration. The $E_{1/2}$ for the quasireversible wave was calculated by Gellings⁴ method. In all the cases except for the ethyl acetate medium, the reduction was found to be diffusion controlled, which is apparent from the linear plots of the

diffusion current vs \sqrt{h} , which pass through the origin.

Lingane⁵ treatment of the observed polarographic data revealed the formation of 1 : 1 Tl(I)-bipyridyl complexes in all the media (aqueous and aquo-organic). The value of stability constants in different media are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1

	Water	DMF	Ethanol	Ethyl acetate	Dioxane
log β	2.50	2.63	2.70	2.75	2.92
Dielectric constant	81.0	39.7	24.3	6.02	2.21

This indicates that the stability of the complex species is enhanced with the lowering of the dielectric constant of the medium as observed by others⁶⁻¹¹.

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Redox Studies on Hydrazine Sulphate Sorbed Zinc Silicate

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INORGANIC ion-exchangers have found many important applications. They are being extensively used for redox purposes in modern laboratories. The definite advantage of redox ion-exchangers over the conventional methods of oxidation or reduction is their insolubility in the medium of reaction, thus the interferences caused by the unreacted redox substances are avoided. The oxidizing or reducing

substances can be easily separated from the substances with which they have reacted.

The few inorganic ion-exchangers to have been used for redox studies are zirconium molybdate¹, zirconium metatungstate², zirconium phosphoiodate³ and a few others⁴⁻⁶. A new class of ion-exchangers have recently been prepared by immobilizing some complexing agents on the common ion-exchangers^{7,8}. The studies on such products, however, have been made only towards achieving separations of analytical importance⁹⁻¹⁰. In the present studies, we have prepared a new redox material by the sorption of a reducing agent, hydrazine sulphate, on zinc silicate, a strong adsorbent. The successful reduction of Fe(III), Mo(VI), V(V), Ce(IV), Sb(V) and Cr(VI) has been achieved quantitatively using the above redox material.

Experimental

Zinc nitrate (M. Merck), sodium silicate (Riedel) and hydrazine sulphate (Merck) were used. All other reagents were of analytical grade. Zinc silicate was prepared by mixing a 0.1 M solution of zinc nitrate and a 0.1 M solution of sodium silicate. The white precipitate so obtained was kept standing for 24 hr at room temp. The precipitate was then filtered, washed and dried at 40°. The dried product was kept immersed in a solution of hydrazine sulphate for another 24 hr. Excess of hydrazine sulphate was washed out with demineralized water and the product dried in an oven at 40°.

The capacity of zinc silicate to take up hydrazine sulphate from its aqueous solution was estimated by shaking a predetermined quantity of hydrazine sulphate solution with 1.0 g of untreated zinc silicate for 6 hr, estimating the amount of hydrazine sulphate remaining in the supernate (0.05M KBrO₃ solution using indigo as indicator¹¹), and calculating the difference.

Chemical stability : 500 mg of the hydrazine sulphate sorbed zinc silicate was shaken with the appropriate solvent for 6 hr at room temp. The amount of hydrazine released into the solution was determined in the supernatant liquid in the manner mentioned above.

Redox studies : Reductions of Fe(III), Mo(VI), V(V), Ce(IV), Cr(VI) and Sb(V) to their respective lower oxidation states were performed by passing their solutions through a column containing 0.5, 1 or 2 g of hydrazine sulphate sorbed zinc silicate on a glass wool support. The effluent was collected in dil. H₂SO₄ solution to avoid air-oxidation of the reduced products. The dissolved oxygen in the H₂SO₄ solution was driven out by adding a small quantity of sodium carbonate. Fe(II) and Mo(III) obtained as effluent, were determined by titrating with a standard solution of KMnO₄^{12,13}. V(V)¹⁴, Ce(VI)¹⁵, Sb(V)¹⁶ and Cr(VI)¹⁷ were determined iodometrically before and after the passage through the exchanger column. The amount initially taken